

Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model

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KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence (AI), Deep Neural Networks (DNNs), Speech Recognition, Human-Machine Interaction (HMI), Precision, Recall.

ABSTRACT

Speech Recognition is a kind of technology which allows the user to operate the electronic device through spoken word instead of using different tools such as keystrokes, button and keyboard etc. Advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) have significantly improved Human-Machine Interaction (HMI), especially with technologies that convert speech into executable actions. It is the process of enabling a computer to recognize and revert to the sounds produced in human speech. Speech recognition is also known as automatic speech recognition (ASR). This paper presents, Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model. In this study, the dataset with 120h of audio which consist of sentences with a maximum of 15 words was used for the model training. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) network is used in this paper for Speech Recognition. Precision, recall and WER (Word Error Rate) are the used parameters for performance analysis. The experimental results demonstrate that the proposed method successfully detects the speech signals and achieves seamless classification performance compared to other conventional speech recognition algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Speech Recognition is a kind of technology which allows the user to operate the electronic device through spoken word instead of using different tools such as keystrokes, button and keyboard etc. Speech recognition software convert the words and phrases which is spoken by user into machine-readable format so that user can easily operate the device through speech [1].

Speech recognition which is also known as automatic speech recognition (ASR). The main objective of

developing speech recognition is any people whether it is technical or non-technical can easily operate the device. As well as an illiterate which have no knowledge about device and its parts they can be operated it very easily [2]. Speech recognition is basically designed for a single user.

Today, human interaction with machines use devices like mouse and keyboards which depend much on hand movements, the speech technology can change the norms by allowing interaction via speech which is faster,

easy and comfort. Human speech perception starts with receiving speech waveform through the ears. The speech will enter membrane basilar situated in the inner middle ear at which the signal waveform will be analyzed and produced spectrum signal. The spectrum signal will enter neural transducer which converts the signal to neural activities at the ear's nerve [3]. The neural signal activities are translated into language code and the message will be sent to the brain for perception.

Research in speech processing and communication for the most part, was motivated by peoples desire to build mechanical models to emulate human verbal communication capabilities. Speech is the most natural form of human communication and speech processing has been one of the most exciting areas of the signal processing. Speech recognition technology has made it possible for computer to follow human voice commands and understand human languages. The main goal of speech recognition area is to develop techniques and systems for speech input to machine. Speech is the primary means of communication between humans. For reasons ranging from technological curiosity about the mechanisms for mechanical realization of human speech capabilities to desire to automate simple tasks which necessitates human machine interactions and research in automatic speech recognition by machines has attracted a great deal of attention for sixty years [4]. Based on major advances in statistical modeling of speech, automatic speech recognition systems today find widespread application in tasks that require human machine interface, such as automatic call processing in telephone networks, and query based information systems that provide updated travel information, stock price quotations, weather reports, Data entry, voice dictation, access to information: travel, banking, Commands, Avoinics, Automobile portal, speech transcription, Handicapped people (blind people) supermarket, railway reservations etc.

Advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) have significantly improved human-machine interaction (HMI), especially with technologies that convert speech into executable actions. automatic speech recognition (ASR) emerges as a leading communication technology in HMI, extensively utilized by corporations and service providers for facilitating interactions through AI platforms like chatbots and digital assistants [5]. Spoken language forms the core of these inter actions,

emphasizing the necessity for sophisticated speech processing in AI systems tailored for ASR. This paper presents, Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model. In this study, the dataset with 120h of audio was used for the model training. Finally, Precision, recall and WER (Word Error Rate) are the used parameters for performance analysis.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: section II presents literature survey, Section III explains the described Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model. Results and discussions are presented in section IV, and finally, Section V concludes the study by summarizing the findings.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In [6] focuses on developing an automatic speech recognition system for English lectures, which involves summarizing the content and providing Japanese subtitles. Subtitling the entire audio of an English lecture could hinder comprehension and readability, so a summarization system is desired. By employing the DNN-HMM based speech recognition system, we achieved an 88% word accuracy for recognizing TED lecture speeches. Speech translation results showed a lower BLEU score of approximately 14% compared to text translation.

In [7] exploit a hierarchical Bayesian interpretation for language modeling, based on a nonparametric prior called Pitman-Yor process. This offers a principled approach to language model smoothing, embedding the power-law distribution for natural language. Experiments on the recognition of conversational speech in multiparty meetings demonstrate that by using hierarchical Bayesian language models, we are able to achieve significant reductions in perplexity and word error rate. In [8], two techniques of automatic speech recognition system training on noised speech are compared with technique of training on clean speech. The comparing has been made by means of speech recognition accuracy measure, with usage of fourteen kinds of noise. It is shown that training on noised speech allows reaching the 95% recognition accuracy for minimal signal-to-noise ratio 10 dB, whereas training on clean speech allows reaching the same recognition accuracy for minimal signal-to-noise ratio 20 dB.

In [9] focuses on the role of speech recognition technology in speech therapy for children with

pronunciation disorders. A simple web game was designed to improve pronunciation of phonemes through children's rhymes. To improve the recognition of children's speech, a model was trained on a children's speech corpus, as conventional systems are optimized for adults. The newly trained model significantly improved the accuracy of speech recognition. In [10] first constructs a comprehensive dataset for Vietnamese Audio-visual Speech Recognition (VASR). A ViAVSP-LLM speech recognition system consisting of an AV-HuBERT encoder and VinaLLaMA decoder is then proposed. Comparative experiments conducted using current audio-only speech recognition models show that the addition of visual data significantly improves the speech recognition accuracy.

III. AI BASED SPEECH RECOGNITION MODEL

The block diagram of Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model is shown in Figure 1.

In this study, the dataset with 120h of audio was used for the model training. The dataset includes speech audio recordings which consist of sentences with a maximum of 15 words with a total length of approximately 120h. In addition, the dataset includes a large amount of different text for use in developing the language model. In addition, the dataset includes a large amount of different text for use in developing the language model. Over 90,650 utterances, 415,780 words, and 65,810 unique words that were included in the text corpus were collected, resulting in around 120 h of transcribed speech data.

Figure 1. Block diagram of AI based Speech Recognition model

In addition to a typical, useful signal, various types of noise are present. As noise negatively affects the quality of speech recognition systems, dealing with noise is a pressing issue. Two types of digital filters are used to reduce the noise levels in the system: a line filter and an initial filter. A linear filter can be considered a combination of low- and high-frequency filters as it captures all low and high frequencies. Initial filtering is applied to minimize the impact of local disturbances on the characteristic markings that are used for subsequent identification. A speech signal must be passed through a low-pass filter for spectral alignment.

Segmentation is the process of dividing a speech signal into discrete, non-overlapping fragments. The signal is usually divided into speech units such as sentences, words, syllables, phonemes, or even smaller phonetic units. The segmentation of recordings that contain the utterances of numerous speakers may consist of attributing pieces of utterances to particular speakers. The term "segment-stations" is sometimes used to refer to a division of the speech signal into frames prior to its parameterization.

Mel-frequency Cepstral coefficients (MFCC) is the most common method for extracting speech features. The human ear is a nonlinear system concerning how it perceives the audio signal. In order to cope with the change in frequency, the Mel-scale was developed to make a linear model of the human auditory system. Only frequencies in the range of [0,1] kHz can be transformed to the Mel-scale, while the remaining frequencies are considered to be logarithmic.

The features extracted by the model are then used to train the Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) to recognize speech. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have significantly advanced the field of automatic speech recognition (ASR) by enabling systems to learn complex patterns from large volumes of speech data. DNNs work by using a hierarchy of layers to model complex relationships between the input speech and the

corresponding text output. A DNN is a multi-layered neural network composed of an input layer, several hidden layers, and an output layer. In speech recognition, the input typically consists of acoustic features such as MFCC (Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients), while the output represents phonemes, characters, or words.

Finally, Precision, recall and WER (Word Error Rate) are the used parameters for performance analysis. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have significantly detects the speech signals.

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

In this section, the performance of Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model is evaluated. In this study, the dataset with 120h of audio which consist of sentences with a maximum of 15 words was used for the model training. Precision, recall and WER are the used parameters for performance analysis.

The precision is the ratio of the number of correctly predicted positive observations to the total number of predicted positive observations. Equation 1 represents the precision parameter.

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (1)$$

The recall is the ratio of the number of correctly predicted positive observations to the total number of observations in the actual class. It is expressed in equation 2,

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (2)$$

Where, TP denotes the number of true positives, FP denotes the number of false positives, and FN denotes the number of false negatives.

Accuracy may be measured in terms of performance accuracy which is usually rated with word error rate (WER). Word error rate is a common metric of the performance of a speech recognition. The WER is derived from the Levenshtein distance, working at the word level instead of the phoneme level. This problem is solved by first aligning the recognized word sequence with the reference (spoken) word sequence using dynamic string alignment. Word error rate can then be computed as in equation 3:

$$WER = \frac{S + D + I}{N} \quad (3)$$

Where, S is the number of substitutions, D is the number of the deletions, I is the number of the insertions and N is the number of words in the reference.

The comparative performance analysis of described Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model (DNN) with other models of Speech Recognition using Decision Tree (DT) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) is represented in below Table 1.

Table 1: Comparative Performance Analysis

Speech Recognition model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	WER (%)
DT	84	86	35
KNN	86	89	29
DNN	96	97	4

Figure 2 represents the Precision parameter comparative analysis for described Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model (DNN) with other models of Speech Recognition using DT and KNN. X-axis represents the classification models and Y-axis represents percentage of parameter value. From figure 2 it is clear that precision of described model is high compared to other models. Comparative performance analysis of recall parameter for described Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model (DNN) with other models of Speech Recognition using DT and KNN is represented in below Figure 3, in which Y-axis shows the percentage value and X-axis denotes classification models. Recall parameter of DNN model is high than other models.

Figure 2. Comparative analysis for precision parameter

Figure 3. Comparative analysis for Recall parameter

WER parameter comparative analysis graphical representation is shown in Figure 4. X-axis represents the classification models and Y-axis represents percentage value. DNN model achieves less WER value than other two models.

Figure 4. Comparative analysis for WER parameter

Therefore from overall results, described Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model is efficient in terms of all parameters. Achieved parameters for described model are WET as 4%, precision as 96% and recall as 97%.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model is described. Speech Recognition System (SRS) is growing day by day and has unlimited applications. Speech recognition is an essential research aspect of speech signal processing and a vital

human-computer interaction technique. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) network is used in this paper for Speech Recognition. Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have significantly advanced the field of automatic speech recognition (ASR) by enabling systems to learn complex patterns from large volumes of speech data. In this study, the dataset with 120h of audio which consist of sentences with a maximum of 15 words was used for the model training. Mel-frequency Cepstral coefficients (MFCC) is the most common method for extracting speech features. Precision, recall and WER are the used parameters for performance analysis. Achieved parameters for described model are WET as 4%, precision as 96% and recall as 97%. Therefore from overall results, described Artificial Intelligence based Speech Recognition model is efficient in terms of all parameters.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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